

Fertilisers from fish processing and aquaculture production waste: An ecofriendly alternative for crop production?

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1. INTRODUCTION

The production of mineral fertilisers causes several sustainability issues: while the manufacturing of nitrogen fertilisers requires high energy input, phosphorus fertilisers depend on the extraction of phosphate rock from finite deposits (Zhang, Akyol, and Meers 2023). In a circular economy, fertiliser production should thus be shifted towards the valorisation of so far unused biowaste streams from various sources (Chojnacka, Moustakas, and Witek-Krowiak 2020; Zhang, Akyol, and Meers 2023). An increasingly important waste stream originates from fish processing and aquaculture production. In this study, we analyse the environmental impacts of the production and application of bio-based fertilisers (BBFs) produced from fish processing and aquaculture waste and compare them to the production and use of mineral fertiliser.

2. METHODS

The goal of the life cycle assessment (LCA) was to compare 1) the environmental impacts of BBF production and 2) BBF application in crop production with those arising from mineral fertilisers. The scope of the LCA was cradle-to-farm gate assuming burden-free waste streams and applying economic allocation for co-products of the BBFs. As functional units, 1 kg of BBF and 1 kg of crop product (wheat grain, ryegrass and broccoli) were selected. Five impact categories were analysed in detail. Data on BBF production were obtained from industrial and pilot production facilities. Data of the latter was upscaled to industrial production, guided by the framework of van der Hulst et al. (2020). For the LCA of crop production, the Excel-based FarmLCA tool was used, that models field emissions, draws inventory data from ecoinvent and assesses impacts based on "IMPACT World+". The potential change in crop yield was determined from pot and field trials performed with the BBFs, calculating their agronomic mineral fertiliser equivalent (MFE). The reference inventories for mineral fertiliser were taken from ecoinvent and matched with the NPK content of the BBFs for the comparison.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results from the BBF production revealed a mixed picture (see Table 1): In comparison with their corresponding mineral fertiliser reference, BBF 4 and 5 showed generally lower environmental impacts while BBF 2 and 3 exhibited mostly higher impacts. BBF 1 performed better for some impact categories, but worse in others. Especially the transport of waste to the BBF production facility, energy intense dewatering or drying processes and packaging affected environmental performance of the BBF production negatively. Most of the BBFs exhibited a better agronomic performance when used as P fertilisers compared to the use as N fertiliser. However, BBF-related yields were generally low and resulted in higher environmental impacts.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary results of this study show that the environmental benefits of BBFs compared to mineral fertilisers depend strongly on the production process of fertilisers, but also on their agronomic performance. Therefore, BBFs can be part of the circular economy, but their environmental performance should be further optimized focussing on transport, water removal as well as agronomic performance.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project SEA2LAND is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (GA no. 101000402). We would like to thank Corinne Andreola, Marie Soone, Tommy C. Olsen, Laure Candy, Clement Chastrette, Christine Raynaud, Monica Gutierrez, Haizea Domínguez, Joaquin Romero, Iñaki Aramburu, Jingsi Zhang, Çağrı Akyol, Liina Edesi, Tiina Talve, Marta Aranguren and Sarah Symanczik for providing data, Nicolas Wittman for support in the modelling and Saioa Ramos for reviewing inventory data.

6. REFERENCES

- Chojnacka K., Moustakas K., and Witek-Krowiak A. 2020. Bio-Based Fertilizers: A Practical Approach towards Circular Economy. *Bioresource Technology* 295.
- van der Hulst, M.K., Huijbregts M.A.J., van Loon N., Theelen M., Kootstra L., Bergesen J.D., and Hauck M. 2020. A Systematic Approach to Assess the Environmental Impact of Emerging Technologies: A Case Study for the GHG Footprint of CIGS Solar Photovoltaic Laminate. *Journal of Industrial Ecology* 24(6):1234–49.
- Zhang J., Akyol Ç., and Meers E. 2023. Nutrient Recovery and Recycling from Fishery Waste and By-Products. *Journal of Environmental Management* 348.

Table 1. Environmental impacts of producing 1 kg of BBF relative to their corresponding mineral fertilizer reference with the same NPK concentration

No	Case study	BBF description	Climate change, short term	Freshwater eutrophication	Marine eutrophication	Mineral resources use	Terrestrial acidification
1	Estonia	BBF granules from bokashi fermentation	59%	159%	31%	249%	24%
2	Spain	NPK solution with amino acids from acid autolysis	567%	47%	232%	424%	122%
3	Italy	Hydrolysate from enzymatic hydrolysis	619%	676%	173%	617%	386%
4	Norway	Pelleted fish sludge	148%	1%	26%	82%	29%
5	France	Solid BBF from extrusion	84%	1%	25%	89%	24%